

KEVLAR® Aramid as a Fiber Reinforcement with Emphasis on Aircraft

P. R. Langston

Du Pont Company, Centre Road Building, Wilmington, DE 19898, U.S.A.

Fiber-reinforced advanced composites for aircraft could be considered an old technology within the aircraft industry's short history. However, advanced composite acceptance as a viable material in aircraft construction is recent, closely paralleling the rapid escalation of fuel prices. Jet fuel increases from 13.8 cents/gallon in 1973 to \$1.10/gallon today have raised the fuel cost, as a percent of direct operating cost for airlines, from 18% to more than 50%. Aircraft manufacturers have responded by improving fuel efficiency of new commercial jets by 40% over older aircraft still in use today. Aircraft manufacturers accomplished these savings by developing more efficient engines, optimizing aerodynamic design and minimizing weight.

The major contributions of advanced composites to date have been reduced weight and lowered manufacturing costs, but equally importantly opened the technology to make additional reductions in both weight and cost as we move into more primary aircraft structures and automatic manufacturing techniques.

The objective of this paper is to put KEVLAR® into perspective as far as its contribution to improving aircraft structures today, what is presently happening, and some projections for the future.

Since the initial samples of PRD 49 from our 1MM pound market development facility were first evaluated by the aircraft industry in 1971, we have steadily expanded our production facilities to meet market requirements, reaching our current 15MM pound capability in 1978. In the latter part of 1982 we will bring onstream an additional 30MM pounds of capacity which should be sufficient to meet projected industry needs into the mid-'80's. Even now we are looking at what the worldwide market needs will be beyond the mid-'80's to insure honoring our commitment to meet the ever-growing KEVLAR needs of the aircraft and aerospace industries.

We at Du Pont are as equally concerned as you are with the rapid changes of prices brought on by oil prices and the inability of industry productivity to offset rising wage costs. It is difficult to predict what these cost pressures will do to the future pricing of KEVLAR; however, we expect that the

*Du Pont Registered Trademark

price of KEVLAR will remain relatively level in constant dollars and the economies of scale, attendant with the expansion to 45MM pound capacity, will allow us to attain the profit margins on which we based our sizable investment in KEVLAR.

The relatively quick acceptance of KEVLAR by aircraft designers as a plastic reinforcement for aircraft structures has been driven by the low density of KEVLAR, along with a good balance of other physical properties.

Fig. 1 shows the relative fiber densities of the various reinforcement fibers.

Figure 1

FIBER DENSITIES

	DENSITY (G/CM ³)	DENSITY (LB/IN ³)
KEVLAR® 49 ARAMID	1.44	0.052
GRAPHITE	1.6-2.0	0.058-0.072
"S"-GLASS	2.48	0.090
"E"-GLASS	2.54	0.092
BORON	2.68	0.097

DENSITY GRADIENT TUBE TECHNIQUE - ASTM D1505

Because KEVLAR is almost one-half the density of fiberglass and 10-20% lighter than carbon fibers, KEVLAR is often the choice of designers because of the weight advantage.

Figure 2

When these two properties, tensile strength and density, are put together, you find that KEVLAR 29 and KEVLAR 49 have the highest strength-to-weight ratio of any material commercially available. In Figure 2,

specific tensile strength, that is tensile strength divided by density, is plotted against specific tensile modulus, modulus divided by density. KEVLAR 29 and KEVLAR 49 are well above other reinforcing fibers on a specific strength basis. For specific modulus, both KEVLAR 29 and KEVLAR 49 fit between fiberglass and graphite. You see the striking contrast KEVLAR 49 has compared with other organic fibers, and even to conventional steel and aluminum materials.

In specific tensile strength, you will note that KEVLAR is 5X stronger than steel and > 10X stronger than aluminum, and KEVLAR 49 is 3X stiffer than steel or aluminum on a specific modulus basis.

Significant advantages are seen for KEVLAR 49 in density and stiffness over glass. Other laminate properties, with the exception of compressive strength, are in good balance. While unidirectional composites of KEVLAR 49 tested in tension have a linear stress-strain curve to failure, when tested in compression their behavior is elastic at a low strain and plastic at high strains. This unique compressive behavior of KEVLAR 49 compared with inorganic reinforcing fibers is fundamental to its metal-like ductility which is illustrated in a 3-point bending test (Figure 3).

Figure 3
UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE BENDING STRESS/STRAIN CURVES (IN EPOXY RESIN)

Figure 4
THE EFFECT OF ELEVATED TEMPERATURE ON THE TENSILE STRENGTH OF ROVING STRANDS OF KEVLAR® 49 ARAMID / EPOXY EXPOSED AT TEMPERATURE SHOWN. TESTED AT ROOM TEMPERATURE PREPARED AND TESTED PER ASTM D2343

Thermal Properties

KEVLAR 49 has good thermal stability, retaining a high percentage of room temperature properties when exposed for long periods up to 355°F (180°C) (Figure 4). The fiber does not melt or support combustion but will carbonize at about 800°F (427°C). At a cryogenic temperature as low as -320°F (-196°C) KEVLAR 49 shows essentially no embrittlement or degradation. KEVLAR 49 also has excellent thermal dimensional stability with a slightly negative coefficient of thermal expansion of $-1.1 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{F}$ ($-2 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$) in the fiber-axis direction. High temperature performance of epoxy laminates reinforced with KEVLAR is limited by the epoxy matrix. NASA, along with Mc Donnell Douglas Aircraft recognizing this limitation, now have in-flight service engine aft fairings on the DC-9 of polyamide laminate structure reinforced with KEVLAR 49. These fairings are exposed to service temperatures up to 400°F.

Figure 5

Other significant and useful mechanical properties of composites of KEVLAR is its excellent cyclic tension-tension fatigue life (Figure 5) and high dampening characteristics (Figure 6). This high dampening quality has led to the statement by some engineers that KEVLAR eats energy. Reference will be made to this quality as we discuss applications where this property makes a major contribution.

Figure 6

DECAY OF FREE VIBRATIONS

	Loss Factor x 10 ⁻⁴
Stainless Steel	6
Graphite/Epoxy	17
Fiberglass/Epoxy	29
KEVLAR® 49/Epoxy	180
Cured Polyester Resin	400

KEVLAR is sold in three different forms. Each was developed for specific type of application (Figure 7).

- Figure 7
- KEVLAR® - Tires
Mechanical Rubber Goods
- KEVLAR® 29 - Ropes and Cables
Ballistics
Coated Fabrics
Tapes and Webbing
Friction Products & Gaskets
- KEVLAR® 49 - Reinforced Plastics
Aircraft and Aerospace
Marine
Sporting Goods
Electrical
Pultrusion

I'll review typical uses for KEVLAR before covering aircraft in more detail.

Automotive

KEVLAR is replacing steel wire in the belts of radial tires (Figure 8). Its unique high tensile properties plus flexibility provide new levels of treadlife, handling and riding comfort in properly designed and constructed tires. Truck tires reinforced with KEVLAR can provide up to 18% weight savings per tire. Lower rolling resistance is an added benefit which can result in improved fuel economy.

Figure 8

Figure 9

Even steel drive chains are being replaced on motorcycles with elastomeric products reinforced with KEVLAR because of high energy transfer efficiency and low noise (Figure 9).

KEVLAR 29 is enabling the automotive companies to help eliminate the potential environmental and health hazards associated with asbestos. A small amount of KEVLAR 29 can serve as a cost effective reinforcing fiber replacement for asbestos and provide higher strength and greater durability. For example, brake linings and clutch facings reinforced with KEVLAR 29 have longer wear life and are stronger than ones of asbestos. Gaskets reinforced with KEVLAR 29 are being used for engine heads and manifolds, and starter motor commutators are molded with phenolic resin reinforced with KEVLAR 29 (Figure 10).

Figure 10

The remarkable strength-to-weight ratio of KEVLAR 49 allows considerable reduction in auto body weight without sacrificing strength. That's why body panels and other parts made of composites of KEVLAR 49 are used in race cars such as Can Am, Trans Am and Formula One cars (Figure 11).

Figure 11

By using KEVLAR 49, the BMW M1 "Pro-Car" body (Figure 12) has been made 40% lighter with no loss of strength. Also, truck chassis beams made of hybrid composites of KEVLAR 49 and graphite are stronger than steel beams and 60% lighter in weight.

Figure 12

KEVLAR is giving automotive designers the best of both worlds: adding strength and durability to parts while reducing weight to increase fuel efficiency.

Marine

Boat hulls constructed with KEVLAR 49 give a quieter, smoother ride than conventional hulls because of the fiber's ability to dampen vibrations. They have high resistance to repeated impacts; and if a hull reinforced with KEVLAR 49 does fail, it happens gradually and not catastrophically.

In sailboats, the advantages of KEVLAR fibers are three-fold. First, the high strength-to-weight ratio of KEVLAR 49 means lighter and faster boats. Second, the stiffness and vibration damping means smoother and more precise sailing performance. And, third, ropes and standing rigging of KEVLAR 29 are longer lasting and up to 75% lighter than their equivalent in steel wire (Figure 13).

Figure 13

On the rough, pounding seas of the ocean racing circuit, the roughness and durability of KEVLAR 49 has been proved by KAAMA, the offshore racer driven by Betty Cook, former World Open Class power boat racing champion. KAAMA, reinforced with KEVLAR 49 has raced competitively in 24 events, a remarkable feat for any boat in this grueling sport. Typically this is twice as long as the life of a boat constructed of fiberglass and exposed to the same exposure (Figure 14).

Figure 14

Commercial fishing boats and military patrol boats (Figure 15) are gaining two major advantages from KEVLAR 49 - increased range and up to 50% lower fuel consumption.

Figure 15

Canoes made with KEVLAR 49 are 20 to 35% lighter than fiberglass or aluminum canoes which makes them easier to portage, launch and maneuver (Figure 16).

Figure 16

Coated fabrics of KEVLAR 29 are finding uses in inflatable boats. Boats made with either urethane or neoprene coated KEVLAR 29 can weigh about half as much as coated nylon boats. And, they don't tear or puncture as easily (Figure 17).

Figure 17

Personnel Protection

More than 300 police officers in the United States and undoubtedly many more officers and military personnel around the world were saved from death or injury because they were wearing body armor of KEVLAR 29 or 49. Designed to stop bullets fired from most common handguns, "soft" body armor of KEVLAR 29 or 49 is notably lighter in weight than old-fashioned ballistic apparel. This reduction in weight provides police officers with an effective body armor that's inconspicuous under the uniform, and comfortable enough to wear routinely on an everyday basis in all climates (Figures 18 and 19).

Figure 18

Figure 19

Flak jackets and helmets are among the military uses for KEVLAR 29. The new U.S. Army helmet, the first design change since World War II, is more resistant to shrapnel than the old steel helmet, thanks to KEVLAR 29. Other military applications include rigid armor for protecting aircraft, ships, tanks and mobile shelters (Figures 20 and 21).

Figure 20

Figure 21

Work gloves which offer exceptional cut resistance without sacrificing manual dexterity or comfort have been developed from fabrics of KEVLAR 29. Laboratory test results have shown that it takes one and a half times the force to cut and two times the force to puncture fabrics of KEVLAR 29 than for similar weight fabrics of cotton (Figure 22).

Figure 22

High temperature resistance and low thermal conductivity are two more reasons why gloves of KEVLAR 29 give better protection. The fiber is inherently flame resistant and begins to char at about 800°F (427°C). KEVLAR 29 can withstand limited contact with materials above 1000°F (538°C).

Ropes and Cables

KEVLAR 29 and 49 are being used in numerous rope and cable applications. They are replacing steel wire in two basic wire cable products - wire rope which is used in applications ranging from small guy wires to very large marine anchor lines, and electromechanical cables (Figure 23) such as fiber optics and sub-sea communications cables. Also soft cordage producers are replacing nylon and polyester fibers with KEVLAR 29 in applications requiring high strength and low stretch. Since no commercial fiber has a higher specific strength, KEVLAR 29 can offer increased payloads and permit easier handling with smaller, lighter rope and cable systems.

Figure 23

An example is a non-rusting mooring line of KEVLAR 29 that is strong enough to anchor giant offshore oil rigs (Figure 24). In water, cables of KEVLAR 29 are 1/20th the weight of steel cables of the same diameter. KEVLAR 29, therefore, enables rigs to probe greater depths - up to 4,000 feet (1,220 m).

The fiber's strength and stretch resistance make it ideal for yacht lines, tow ropes and tether cables, as well.

Figure 24

Telecommunications systems are taking advantage of the non-magnetic and insulating properties of KEVLAR 29 and 49 as well as their high strength-to-weight ratio. Thin fiber optic cables reinforced with KEVLAR 49 are replacing large diameter copper conductor cables. And balloons serving as antennas for communications systems are connected to earth with tethers of KEVLAR 29.

Aerospace

In aerospace, the first commercial success was on the Trident Missile (Figure 25). All three stages of this missile contain filament wound composite motor cases of KEVLAR. Engineers were able to save about 800 lbs. by replacing S glass with KEVLAR.

Figure 25

Figure 26 shows the filament wound motor cases used on the Trident Missiles. Similar configuration and missile casement construction are and will be used for missiles in production and under design.

Figure 26

The middle stage of the Trident is shown in Figure 27.

Figure 27

Resulting from the missile developments are pressure bottles reinforced with KEVLAR. Figure 28 shows two round cylinders like the 23 used on the NASA space shuttle and a cylindrical bottle which is used on the Boeing 747 to inflate escape slides. The 747 bottle reinforced with KEVLAR weighing 20 lbs. replaced a 42 pound metal bottle.

Figure 28

The Ariane satellite launcher (Figure 29) is the ultimate in European missile technology.

The apogee engine (Figure 30) which places the satellite in orbit has been developed by Societe Europeenne de Propulsion (S.E.P.) in France. The casing is made by winding rovings of KEVLAR fiber impregnated with epoxy resin. The use of KEVLAR allows up to 35 percent weight reduction versus S-glass.

Figure 30

The second stage of the French M-4 Missile has its motor case reinforced with KEVLAR (Figures 31 and 32). SNIAS uses 148 kilos (330 lbs.) of roving which is treated and impregnated before winding of the motor case to achieve up to 35 percent weight reduction versus S-glass fiber.

Figure 31

Figure 32

Qualified KEVLAR motor case
Design, Technologies:

- ① - winding material: Kevlar 49-4560 densers / epoxy prepress*
- ② - bosses: aluminum alloy
- ③ - skirts: carbon cloth
- ④ - end rings: aluminum alloy
- ⑤ - Insulator: fabricated by AQUITAINE (design and raw material are supplied by the motor contractor)

*prepress: Aquitaine and Laboratoire de la S.E.P. Aquitaine Centre

Aircraft

All major airframe manufacturers are using KEVLAR in their aircraft. Emphasized in this talk are key programs that I feel are of the most interest.

KEVLAR has found a wide range of applications in the interior and exterior of commercial aircraft. In the interior, KEVLAR is basically used for all the fiber reinforced plastics; and on the exterior, all of the parts pictured are specified for in-flight evaluation (Figure 33).

Figure 33

Lockheed, with NASA sponsorship, was the first commercial aircraft manufacturer to commit major, large exterior parts to KEVLAR. Lockheed committed the L-1011-500 to this part pictured; then, subsequently committed of KEVLAR to their other models the same parts (Figure 34).

Figure 34

TriStar
L1011

**KEVLAR-49
COMPOSITE
APPLICATIONS**

AILERON T.E. WEDGE
RUDDER T.E. WEDGE
ELEVATOR T.E. WEDGE
"FRISBEE" FAIRING
WING L.E. PANELS
PYLON FAIRINGS
WING TO BODY FAIRINGS (OVER AND UNDER)
WING FIXED T.E. PANELS
PYLON FAIRINGS
WING T.E. FLAP WEDGE

TOTAL KEVLAR-49 COMPOSITE APPLICATIONS - 2500 POUNDS.
WEIGHT SAVED - 805 POUNDS.

The end result was a commitment to 2500M lbs. of KEVLAR laminates to the exterior surface with a 805 lb. weight savings.

Table 1 summarizes the various interior and exterior parts now being fabricated with KEVLAR 49 on the L-1011-500.

TABLE 1. PRODUCTION COMPONENTS OF KEVLAR 49 ON THE L-1011-500

Part Category	Fabricator	Kevlar-49 Fabric Style	Resin	General Construction, Remarks
Wing-body Fairings	Heath-Tecna	281 and 120	Epoxy (250°F Curing)	Primarily sandwich panels with core of Nomex. Skins 0.015-0.02 in. thick. Sizes range up to 20 ft ² in area. Total no. parts approx. 55. A few small solid laminate parts also included.
Wing Fixed Leading Edge Panels, Access Doors, Fixed Trailing Edge Panels	AVCO	285 with 120 Fiberglass	Epoxy (250°F Curing)	Sandwich panels with core of Nomex, typically 0.75 in. thickness. Skins typically 0.015 in. thick. Leading edge components have extremely sharp contours; doors and trailing edge panels relatively flat. A few solid laminate leading edge parts also included. Total no. parts approx. 90. Size ranges up to 66 by 36 in. (leading edges), and 90 by 20 in. (trailing edges).
Rudder Trailing Edge, Elevator Trailing Edge, Diverter Fairing	Lockheed-Georgia Co.	281 and 120, some limited usage of 285	Epoxy (250°F Curing)	Rudder and elevator trailing edges are full depth, wedge shaped honeycomb panels with maximum depth approx. 2 in. Skin thickness 0.025 in. Length up to 20 feet. Diverter fairing also sandwich construction with 0.025 in. skins and core of Nomex. Components all have some areas of sharp contour.
Ceiling Panels Dividers	Lockheed-California Co.	285 with some 120	Flame retardant epoxy (250°F Curing)	Sandwich panels with core of Nomex. Ceiling panels curved, typically 0.4 in. thick with 0.010 in. thick skins. Dividers primarily flat panels ranging from 0.25-1.0 in. thick with skin thicknesses from 0.015-0.03 in.
Stowage Compartment Backs and Pans	Lockheed-California Co.	285	Phenolic (for low smoke characteristics)	Matched die molded laminate construction with corrugations. Thickness 0.03 in.

Boeing, with their new generation of fuel efficient 767-757 jets, was the next major passenger jet manufacturer to commit exterior components to KEVLAR and then pioneered in the development of hybrids of KEVLAR/graphite to best utilize the properties of both fibers.

ADVANCED COMPOSITE SUMMARY

Kevlar	Stabilizer Tips T E Flap Linkage Fairings Strut Fairings ECS Ducts Cargo Liner Stowage Bins Emergency Escape System Components Lavatories Closets Partitions Inboard Flap Debris Protection
Hybrid	Wing Fixed T E Panels Cowl Components Wing to Body Fairing Main Landing Gear Doors Nose Landing Gear Doors Stabilizer Fixed T E Panels Stabilizer Seal Plates Lower L E Access Panels
Graphite	Spoilers Inboard and Outboard Outboard Ailerons Inboard Aileron Panels Rudder Elevators

Boeing was the first to commit production parts to composites; in early models, the composite was a replacement for metal. Some keys to Boeing's design was to utilize the stiffness properties of the graphite and damage tolerance and corrosion resistance of KEVLAR. Boeing was able to reduce the weight of their 767 by 2028 pounds with the parts noted in Figures 35 and 36.

Figure 35 and Figure 36

767 Composite Structural Applications

767 Composite Interiors and Systems Applications

Hybrid Main Landing Gear Door Being Manufactured by Fuji Heavy Industry

Shown is the Concorde and its interior, where British aerospace used KEVLAR extensively in the sidewalls, overhead storage and ceiling panels, bulkheads, etc. (Figures 38 and 39).

Figure 38

Figure 39

Douglas, in their commitment to their new fuel efficient jet, the DC-9-Super 80, committed the tail cone and wing to body fairing to KEVLAR and engine cowlings to KEVLAR with hat stiffeners made of fabrics of KEVLAR and graphite tapes.

Figure 40

Rohr Industry developed the motor nacelle made with KEVLAR for Douglas and for the Boeing 727 (Figure 41). The weight saved on this nacelle is between 40 and 45% over the metal nacelle it is replacing. The change from metal to composite also resulted in a cost saving.

Figure 41

A further 99 lbs. have been saved in the empennage (Figure 45). The fin leading and trailing edges as well as the tip have been lightened by 77 lbs., the rudder leading edge by 17.5 lbs., and the fin-to-fuselage fairings by 4.5 lbs.

Figure 45

The fin leading edge (Figures 47, 48, and 49) consists of the dorsal fin and parts one, two and three. Because of the dielectric properties required by a radio antenna located underneath the laminates, skins of part one are made from one ply of glass fiber fabric between two plies of KEVLAR.

Figure 46

A 310 Airbus

Composite material application

Figure 47

Figure 48
A 310 Airbus
 Composite material application

Fin leading edge 1
 Section B-B

Weight reduction
 12,5 kg
 24,8% of old design

Figure 49

A 310 Airbus
 Composite material application

Fin leading edge 3

The rudder leading edge (Figures 50 and 51) is 8.2 kilos or 33.9 percent lighter than the original part with glass fiber. It is built as a sandwich laminate with skins of two plies of graphite fiber between two plies of woven KEVLAR.

Figure 50

Figure 51

A 310 Airbus
 Composite material application

Rudder leading edge 1-6
 Section F-F

Weight reduction
 8,2 kg
 33,9% of old design

On the fuselage, 31 lbs. have been gained versus light alloy and 15.5 lbs. versus glass fiber on the fairings of the air-conditioning inlets (Figures 52 and 53). The skins on the core of the honeycomb of NOMEX paper are reinforced with fabrics of KEVLAR fiber.

Figure 52

A 310 Airbus
Composite material application

Air conditioning fairings

Air conditioning fairings			
Weight saving (Kg)			
Light alloy (B2 B4 version)	41	41	
NOMEX and fiber glass	36	36	
NOMEX and KEVLAR	29	29	
ΔW per A/C =	7	14	7

Figure 53

The pylon fairing parts (Figure 54) reinforced with KEVLAR weigh 16 lbs. less than with glass fiber and contribute to the total weight reduction.

Figure 54

A 310 Airbus
Composite material application

Engine pylon fairings

Engine pylon fairings	
Weight saving:	Kg
Fiber glass	26.5 Kg
KEVLAR	19 Kg
ΔW per AC =	7.5 Kg

The same components will also gradually equip the A 300-600 aircraft which will come into service in early 1984. This is an advanced version of the A 300 B2-4 incorporating new technology features developed for the A 310. There also, KEVLAR will replace glass fiber, which had originally been specified in the 1970s before the aramid fiber was generally known.

Further weight reduction on the A 310 and A 300 aircraft by the use of common composite parts reinforced with KEVLAR fiber, alone or with graphite, is envisaged by Airbus Industries

Jet Engines

The high level of protection against fragment impact provided by KEVLAR enables Rolls Royce to achieve a 25% weight savings versus steel using KEVLAR woven fiber in the production of the containment ring of their RB 211/535C turbofan engine (Figure 55). This engine is being developed to equip the new fuel efficient Boeing 757 and similar transport aircraft. Rolls Royce has developed with a British weaver a fabric with special curvature to take best advantage of the energy absorption characteristics of KEVLAR fiber.

Figure 55

The acoustic panels of the CFM 56 modern technology turbofan engine (Figure 56) are reinforced with KEVLAR fiber by SNECMA, the French partner of General Electric in the CFM International Company.

Figure 56

These panels (Figures 57 and 58) which are located in the fan stator casing on both sides of the fan blade tip-seal, dampen the fan noise. They contribute to the low take-off noise level of modern commercial jet aircraft. In addition, these parts must withstand erosion by rain, hail and sand and have high aerodynamic efficiency for undisturbed air flow to the fan.

Figure 57

Figure 58

Aluminum could not meet these requirements. Consequently, SNECMA took advantage of several physical properties of KEVLAR: resistance to impact and abrasion, vibration damping and light weight. The fiber allows approximately 50 percent weight reduction versus light alloy (Figure 59).

Figure 59

To obtain maximum aerodynamic efficiency, these panels are molded to exact dimensions with multiple plies of epoxy prepreg. Also, special tools have been developed for drilling holes that meet aerodynamic requirements.

DeHavilland has led the growing commuter aircraft industry in use of KEVLAR. With extensive exterior parts, such as the Avionics' Bay (Figure 60), and complete interior including floor of KEVLAR on their 50-passenger, 4-engine prop. Dash 7.

Figure 60

The 36-passenger Dash 8 now in design will see more extensive use of KEVLAR. This will include the complete interior including seats and exterior as shown in Figure 61. Use of KEVLAR in the wing leading in addition to meeting strike requirements will give improved aerodynamics because of the molded in deicing boot (Figure 62).

Figure 61

Figure 62

The design of the Dornier 228 light turboprop utility commuter aircraft (Figures 63 and 64) is also typical of the lightweight principles applied by the Western European aeronautical industry.

Figure 64
Dornier 228

The weight of this aircraft is reduced by 50 kilos (approximately 110 lbs.) by reinforcing laminates with KEVLAR fiber. These composites are specified for exterior structures such as wing trailing edge, the flap track fairings, the aileron trailing edge, the fin leading edge, the fuselage rear cone, and the luggage, access and landing gear doors, where 60 percent of the weight saving is achieved. The same construction technique is applied to interior components. The entire flooring panels have skins in woven KEVLAR over honeycomb of NOMEX paper.

The first radar dome reinforced with KEVLAR was on the Cessna Citation I. The Citation III, now in production, uses KEVLAR in the various fairings plus motor nacelles in addition to the radar dome (Figure 65). Radomes of KEVLAR are now on numerous aircraft with the largest being the retrofit of the Lockheed C-5A which is 16 feet diameter and 10 feet deep.

Figure 65

The passenger seat for Cessna's 402 passenger aircraft is reinforced with KEVLAR. This seat is 13-1/2 lbs. versus the lightest weight metal tube seat which weighed 32 lbs. (Figure 66).

Several seat programs under development by commuter aircraft producers will be commercial shortly.

Figure 66

Helicopters

Sikorsky Helicopters led in the commercial adoption of KEVLAR in reinforced parts in the S-76 commercial helicopter. An overall frame with savings was accomplished by replacing fiberglass and aluminum parts which resulted in a 20% improvement in range.

Figure 67

The S-76 horizontal stabilizer, the first composite stabilizer certified by FAA, is a hybrid combination of KEVLAR and graphite over full-depth honeycomb core of NOMEX, see Figures 68 and 69.

Figure 68

Figure 69

Incorporated in the design of the S-76 cockpit canopy is Sikorsky Aircraft's experience obtained from the manufacture of CH-53 and Black Hawk cockpits.

The cockpit canopy is made of three pre-molded parts of woven material of KEVLAR, bonded together to form the canopy assembly as shown in Figure 70. This assembly consisting of the outer skin, substructure skeleton and door jamb is then mounted directly to the aircraft fuselage.

Figure 70

On a new generation helicopter, SNIAS Dauphin SA 366 G twin engine (Figure 71), which has been purchased by the U. S. Coast Guard, composite materials weigh approximately 680 lbs. and account for 23 percent of the aircraft's empty weight, engines and ancillary systems excluded. KEVLAR is widely used on secondary structures (radome, doors, fairings, cowlings).

Figure 71

SA 366 G DAUPHIN
SNIAS Aérospatiale

The increased use of KEVLAR for the reinforcement of helicopter structures is also illustrated by M.B.B. in Germany (Figures 72 and 73).

Figure 72

**Composite structures
on MBB helicopter fuselage**

	BO 105 CBS	BO 105 M
Wetted area of composite parts	10,3 m ² 32%	11,3 m ² 37%
Wetted area of KEVLAR parts	0 m ² 0%	5,6 m ² 18%

*Percentage of total wet area

Figure 73

**Composite structures
on MBB helicopter fuselage**

	BK 117
Wetted area of composite parts	24,5 m ² 53%*
Wetted area of KEVLAR parts	24,5 m ² 53%*

*Percentage of total wet area

Parts reinforced with the fiber represented 18 percent of the total fuselage wet area on the BO 105 M. This has grown to 53 percent of the M.B.B. Kawasaki BK 117 wet area. The latter aircraft is the first helicopter built with the horizontal stabilizer plane and fins reinforced entirely with KEVLAR fiber (Figure 74).

Figure 74

Shown is a Hughes AAH-64A (Figure 75), close ground support Army helicopter. There has been about twice as much KEVLAR adopted for this helicopter as shown.

Figure 75

The relative size of the pod is best shown in Figure 80. The capacity of the pod is over 1,000 gallons.

Figure 80

Boeing Vertol have built a CH-47 fuselage out of composite for comparison to the incumbent all-metal. The skins are KEVLAR/NOMEX honeycomb and stringers of KEVLAR/graphite hybrids (Figure 81).

Figure 81

TABLE 2. COMPARISONS FOR ALL-COMPOSITE FUSELAGE

Item	Type of Structure	
	Aluminum	Composite
No. of Parts	11,000	1,530
No. of Fasteners	86,000	7,000
Weight (lb)	4,687	3,281

POTENTIAL SAVINGS 33% 46% 65%

Other Aircraft Uses

Pictured is the CASA-120 aircraft (Figure 83) with Hartzell propellers. These composite propellers have structural skins of tapes and fabrics of KEVLAR 49, a foam core and metal hub. They have been certified by the FAA for 1100 hours, or 5 years, whichever comes first. They are continuing to gain additional certification as time is accumulated. Beech King propellers of similar construction have now been FAA certified.

Figure 83

Fiberfloat was the first producer of airplane floats using lamintes of KEVLAR. They are lighter, more durable, and can reduce drag because of improved shape (Figure 84).

Figure 84

Applebay produced the first sail plane with its laminates predominately reinforced with KEVLAR. The Zuni II is 70 lbs. lighter than the same airplane in fiberglass (Figure 85).

Figure 85

One of the first primary structural applications of KEVLAR was on the outer wing panels of the Teledyne Ryan Model 1477 (AQM 34R). One outer wing was 8 foot long and was fabricated by Teledyne and fatigue tested at WPAFB-FDL. Fatigue test showed no failure after 104,000 cycles of (+60% -30% design limited load) simulated aircraft fatigue. This was equivalent to 2.5 life times (Figure 86).

Figure 86

Length: 30 Feet
 Span: 32 Feet
 Height: 7.5 Feet
 Gross Weight: 6,000 Lbs.
 (Approx.)

TRA AQM-34R

In high performance military jets, Siai Marchetti of Italy are leading in adoption of KEVLAR by extensive applications on their S-211 jet trainer.

Figure 87

Applications of KEVLAR[®]
 ■■■■■ Current
 ▒▒▒▒▒ Projected

There are various applications in space where KEVLAR is being used: structural parts for the satellite and antennas that are being used by many broadcasting companies. We see a broad future for KEVLAR in aerospace applications (Figure 88).

Figure 88

